

THE DESIGN OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS OF QUALITY CONTROL IN THE LABORATORY PROCESS IV PT X

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Abstract- The effectiveness and efficiency of the information system is the key aspect that can determine the advances or setbacks of a organization. The organization of the manufacturing industry is inseparable from the it is. Process Laboratory IV is still using spreadsheet based information system so that most of the activities and evaluation are still run manually. This research was conducted to design more efficient quality control information system through implementation of web based application. The system design involves four actors with different authority and access levels to minimize information security issues. Through these conditions various forms of fraud can also be minimized. In addition, the system design also improves the information flow efficiency by eliminating the activity of re-input set point data. It can be concluded that the design of information systems with web-based applications have been able to help improve efficiency and minimize the weaknesses of current existing information systems in the PT X Process Laboratory IV

Index Terms-- Design, Efficiency, Information, Laboratory, System

I. INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness and efficiency of the information system is the key aspect that can determine the advances or setbacks of a organization. The organization of the manufacturing industry is inseparable from the it is. Effective information systems and implemented correctly will affect the the performance of the management in controlling the production system of the manufacturing industry. However, information systems too complex and complicated it can decrease the efficiency of the system the production as a whole. Web-based applications are often used to increase the the effectiveness and efficiency of a process. An example of its application wide enough as to improve the efficiency in the process learning, the electrical energy consumption in the home, as well as on the the process of collecting survey data [. Increased efficiency such occurs because the web-based

application easy to actor involved in the system to carry out their duties. PT X is one of the cement industry in Indonesia and to keep the competitive advantage PT X set up several Laboratory Processes which are responsible for the activity quality control, one of which is a Laboratory Process IV. The Laboratory Process IV still using spreadsheet as an application supporting information systems. It the cause most of the activity and the evaluation of still done manually, so slow the pace of the flow of information. In addition, the use of a spreadsheet open the possibility of various forms of fraud caused by the lack of security services of the default software the. Based on this reason, the design of supporting applications quality control Laboratory Process IV needs to be done as a step to improve the efficiency and reliability of the system. Another positive impact is expected occurrence the simplification of the flow of data and information.

The purpose of the research is to design information systems quality control more efficient and application-based website supporters in the Laboratory Process IV PT X. The design of information systems is not done at once, so the study only focus on the flow of information related to the results of the test material from the Carrier 1 to the Staff Evaluation and the operator of the Central Control Room (CCP).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter contains about the study of literature related to this journal

1. Define information systems analysis and design

Definition of system information can be derived based on the definition of each of its constituent words, the system and information. Defines the system as a collection of some element or elements that are interact to achieve a certain goal. Definition matching is also given by Jogiyanto which describes the system as a network of interconnected for do an activity or complete a particular purpose. The system can be in the form of a group of human, machine, thing, or type of other entities. Meanwhile, information can be defined as a result of processing data that has value or meaning certain. Based on the definition of both words, define information system as a system connecting the needs of daily transaction processing, support operations, management activities and strategies in a

organization to provide the required reports, better for the purposes of internal and certain external parties.

An information system is the result of human design and consisting of various components in an organization to achieve a goal, that serves information useful. Information system is one of the aspects of needed by the organization. Advance or retreat a the organization represented by the effectiveness and efficiency of the system the information used by the organization. The goal of information systems in general, among others: (1) Provides information that can help the process management decision making; (2) Facilitate the execution of daily operations; and (3) Provide information eligible for parties outside the organization, especially regarding the issue of transparency management.

Information systems must be able to support the business strategy company. Business strategy is realized through a series of business processes, so that the business process should ideally is the foundation for the development of information systems. Business processes describe all of the activities implemented in a system. Input, process, output, the actors involved, the flow of data and information can be identified through the depiction of business processes. In addition to the description of the process the business also provides an explanation related activities involved and the relationships between them within reach the purpose of the system and produce the output. Representation of the process business in the form of pictures is a Business Process Diagram. Some of these studies are also presented some of the advantages of using information technology, such as simplify the job, memudahkan promotion, and expand the market.^[8]

Information system design begins by re-design business processes that have been there. The application of web-based applications open the opportunities for increasing the efficiency of the process, so that the redesign is intended to simplify the process business. Business Process Diagrams are used as a guide in the process of re-design. Although effective in show a business process in outline, business process the diagram does not show clearly the interactions that occur between the actor and the system. The interaction is described through use case diagram. Basically the use case is used to describe the function of the system, the involvement and the role of the actor in such a system. Component-common components of a use case diagram, among others: (1) the Actor, is defined as a person or something outside the system that interact with the system to carry out a particular job. The symbol of the “stickman” of the ordinary used to represent the actors. (2) Use case, is a function of a system unit which carry out the transfer of information and change among the actors or units. In the use case diagram, a use case is represented in the form of an ellipse bearing the name of the use case. (3) the Relationship, describe the relationship between two or more actors to use case. A symbol of the relationship usually in the form of a line with or without the arrow. Database design is the process of generating a model of the detailed data from the database, the database design involves the selection of: a column for each table and how the table and the columns interact with each other.^[6]

The static structure of the system model information is described by class diagram, or also often called object modelling. Class the diagram consists of a collection of elements of the model that are static, such as the classes along with the content as well as the relationship between class-class. Each class contained in the system have attribute and method respectively. The identification of the class carried out to define the attribute, method and the relationship between these classes with another class. If a class is defined globally, then other objects can be access the class.^[1]

2. Information systems development life cycle (SDLC)

System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) is a picture of a effort in designing a system that will always move like a wheel, which go through multiple steps or stages include stage investigate, analyze, design, implementation and maintenance. And the next step would be back on stage investigate if it is felt that the existing system is no longer efficient to be applied. Then there is the proverb says that a system is never considered complete and is always open to opportunities to develop in accordance with the development of the era. Sooner or later, such properties must be updated. Figure 2.5. the following describes the stage the cycle of new life begins. Opening with the planning stage (Raymond Mc Leod, 2010:24).

2.1 Step-by-step Methods SDLC

Each step in the SDLC have goals that support the purpose-the purpose of the preparation of the system, namely to construct a system of information efficiently and effective. Steps of SDLC. The company services shall design the process of delivering services that are superior, not bureaucratic and customer-oriented. In high-contact service, the customer is involved in the process of delivering services, so they need to understand their roles well.^[7]

2.1.1. Stage Planning / Investigation

The Planning stage with regard to the preliminary studies to build a system new step by step as follows :

a. Defining the issues that appear in the system

Once the management is aware of the problem, then it should be well understood in order to overcome the problem it. On this step managers should work closely with systems analysts, to identify where is the problem and what the possible the cause.

b. Identify the constraints that exist in general.

Managers and systems analysts create a list of goals the system should be met by a system to satisfy the user and expressed in general.

c. Identify the constraints that exist in general.

The new system will not operate free from constraints and should be identified before the system is completely started.

d. Make a feasibility study.

A feasibility study is an overview on the main factors that will affect the ability of the system to achieve the objectives.

e. Prepare research proposal system.

After the project is viable, it is necessary research system thorough. Systems analysts and designers of preparing the proposal research system that provides the basis of how the manager to determine whether the research system

2.1.2. The Analysis Phase

The analysis system can be defined as a process to understand the system there with the aim to design a new system or update.

a. Announced research system.

When it was announced a research system, then the management should take steps to ensure the cooperation of the parties employees. To provide understanding about the usefulness of the development will be achieved will benefit the employees and the company.

b. Define the information needs of the

Systems analysts study of the information needs to learn the information needs of users involved in a variety of activities gather information by conducting interviews, with the first first in addition to know sehingga good communication as well as can increase enthusiasm among analysts do not only depend on the technical skills but also communication skills among personnel to create friendship between analysts with the user. Systems analyst

c. Prepare draft proposals

d. Define the proposed system performance.

The next step is to specify precisely what should achieved by the system, i.e. the system performance criteria.

2.1.3. Stage Design / system Design.

In the next stage is to design a new system that can runs better, and is expected to overcome the problems that exist and to the extent possible be able to anticipate the possibilities of the future. The benefits of a design system is to provide an overview design (blueprint) complete, as a guide for programmers in developing the application. The design of the physical associated with the technical specifications on the implementation later. The design of the alternatives is done and compare it to get the best alternative in Addition also design output input, database, and application.^[9]

2.1.4. Stage Of Implementation

The application is an activity to obtain and identify the source of the power physical and conceptual to produce a system that works, by doing a few things, namely : planning application, announced the adoption, to get hardware resources, get resources software, setting up the database, setting up the physical facilities, training users, and enter the new system.

2.1.5. The maintenance phase

In the use of the system is deemed necessary to held the maintenance of the system. It those in the know over some of the reasons, among others : intends to fix, maintain a current system, and improve system.

3. RAD

RAD is an approach object oriented towards the development of a system that includes a method development as well as devices software. There are four phases

3.1 Phase of Requirements Planning (Planning Terms)

This phase is the phase of the meeting between the analyzer and the user to identify the purpose of the system will be built as well as identify the terms of the information that will arise to achieve these goals as well as analyze all of the systems that are needed by the user.

3.2 Phase RAD Design Workshop (Workshop Design RAD)

This phase is the phase in shape design workshop RAD between analysts and programmers to designing a system that will built. analysts and programmers work together in building the system and shows its representation in the form of visual design and the patterns work to users of the system. in this phase also the user responds to the prototype that has been designed. Analysis and programmers can improve and analyze module module designed based on the from the response of the system user.

3.3 Phase Instruction (Construction)

The Construction phase is the phase the execution in the form of making the script program and is a continuation of the the second phase. In this phase also showed platform, hardware, and software used. Each design is made on the previous phase, will be enhanced with use the device RAD. After new function available, the new function such shown to the user to get the interaction and revision, furthermore, the analyzer will do changesin any design application based on the instruction from the user.

3.4 Phase Implementation (Implementation)

This phase analyzer work with the user intensively during the workshop, and some design aspects and nontechnical needed. As soon as aspects of this approved and systems built and filtered, the system-new system or part of the system is tested and then introduced to organization.^[3]

4. CASE

Computer Aided Software Engineering is the application of a set of tools and methods to a software system with the desired end result is high quality, defect free, and software products are maintained. It also refers to methods for the development of information systems together with automated tools that can be used in the software development process.

CASE (software engineering computer-aided) is the use of methods with the help of computers to manage and control the software development, especially on large, complex projects involving many software components and people. Use CASE allows designers, code writers, testers, planners, and managers to share a common view of where the project stands at any stage of development.^[4]

5. RUP

RUP is a framework of processes that provide the simulation system in the industry for systems, software, implementation, and management of effective project. RUP is one of the many processes that are contained in the Rational Process Library, which gives the best simulation for the development or project needs. RUP has several stages, namely :

- a. Inception
- b. Elaboration
- c. Construction
- d. Transition

5.1 Inceptionis

The stage to identify the system to be developed. Activities undertaken at this stage include, among others, the analysis of the existing system, the formulation of the target system, the determination of the global architecture of the target, the identification of needs, the formulation of requirements (functional, performance, security, GUI, etc.), the formulation of the testing needs (level unit, integration, system, performance, functionality, security, etc.), UML diagrams, and creating documentation.

5.2 Elaboration

Elaboration is the stage to do the design in full based on the results of the analysis at the stage of inception. Activities undertaken at this stage include, among others, making the design of the architecture of the subsystem (architecture pattern), the design of the system components, design the format of the data (communication protocol), database design, user interface design, modeling UML diagrams(sequence diagram, class, component, deployment, etc.), and the creation of documentation.

5.3 Construction

Construction stage is to implement the results of the design and testing results of the implementation. In the early stages of construction, there is a well done re-examination of the results of the analysis and the design, especially the design on the sequence diagram, class diagram, component and deployment. If the design has been made in accordance with the analysis of the system, then the implementation of the language pemrogramanan can be done. Activities undertaken at this stage include, among others, testing results analysis and design, data collection needs complete implementation (based on the identification of needs in this stage of analysis), determination of the coding pattern used, programming, testing, optimization of programs, documenting the variety of

possible development or further improvement, and manufacturing documentation.

5.4 Transition

Transition is the stage to submit the application system to the user (roll-out), which generally includes training and beta testing of the app.^[5]

III. DISCUSSION

System information to the actual applied on a Laboratory Process IV includes several activities, among others: testing samples using the X-ray machine and STILL, processing the data using spreadsheet software as well as reporting the results of the staff evaluation and operator Central Control Panel (CCP). There are three operators that become actors in a system of such information. Operator 1 is responsible for the data input process. Operators 2 and 3 assigned to conduct quality testing.

Based on the results of observations, there is a looping activity on the operator 1. After receiving the results of tests performed by the Operator 2 and Operator 3 Operator 1 will perform advanced testing using x-ray machine. The test results are transferred to the QCX as input. The results that come from QCX-shaped data on the percentage of oxide chemical and sent to the PC Operator 1 as the input data together with the results of the testing of the Operator 2 and Operator 3. Percentage Data will be processed using spreadsheet software and the Operator 1 will determine the proportion of each material needed in the process. The proportion of the material reported on the staff of the evaluation to be analyzed and evaluated. At the same time, the Operator 1 have to re-enter some of the contents of the report into a new spreadsheet that can be accessed by the Operator of the CCP and this is where the looping activity in question occurred. Looping input data occurred because the Operator of the CCP is only allowed to access a portion of the contents of the report.

Another issue that needs attention is the possibility of the occurrence of fraud committed by the actors in the system. Standard and formulation set out by the staff of the evaluation are stored in the form of a function of the conditional and spreadsheet standard does not provide a security system for the feature. This condition allows all the actors in the system to change the standards and functions conditional there.

System Design Information

Development for information systems quality control laboratory process is focused on improving the efficiency of the system. A web-based application is used to replace your spreadsheet. The issue of looping activity experienced by the Operator 1 can be overcome through the use of web-based applications. Therefore a web-based application that is designed not only acts as a replacement for spreadsheets, but also to provide improvements to the information systems used. Draft improvements to the system can be shown through the Business Process Diagram. The second business process is described through the Business Process Diagram is so clear

difference. Business process proposal to eliminate the activity of the repetition of the input set point data, which is usually done by the Operator 1. The elimination of these activities will reduce the time needed to carry out the whole process, so that will increase the efficiency of the system. In addition, the elimination of the looping will also minimize the potential for human error and writing errors in the data input process.^[1]

IV. CONCLUSION

1. Define information systems analysis and design

Definition of system information can be derived based on the definition of each of its constituent words, the system and information. Defines the system as a collection of some element or elements that are interact to achieve a certain goal.

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RUP is a framework of processes that provide the simulation system in the industry for systems, software, implementation, and management of effective project

6. Preliminary studies of information systems-based spreadsheet that is used on a Laboratory Process IV PT X shows some drawbacks such as: the rate of information flow is sluggish, lack of security level information, as well as the potential for the occurrence of various forms of cheating. This research was conducted to design the information system more efficient through the application of web-based applications. The design involves four actors with the authority and the level of access that is different. These differences will improve the security of information, so that various forms of cheating that involves the manipulation of data by parties other can be minimized. In addition, the design of information systems also eliminate the activity of the repetition of the input set point data, which is usually done by the Operator 1

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